

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Advanced observation methodology for system-level testing of accelerator electronics (AOM-AE)</i>
Project TA identifier	TA10-317
General application	<i>High-energy accelerators</i>
Type of test	SEE, TNID
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Date(s) of the experiment	30.07.2024, 31.07.2024, 17.09.2024, 18.09.2024
Facility	<i>Chiplr (STFC Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, Didcot, UK)</i>
Amount of access granted	24h

Objectives of the experiments

This project is in the framework of the PhD thesis which aims at studying the aspects of system-level testing of electronic equipment for high-energy particle accelerators. The submitted proposal concerns the development of a new approach for system observations, combining the data collection in both hardware and software of the tested system. The collected data will be used to investigate the Total Non-Ionising Dose (TNID) degradation, as well as the Single Event Effects (SEEs) arising at the hardware elements of the system, and will allow to trace down its most vulnerable components. This information presents valuable feedback on the system performance and could be used to improve the radiation tolerance of the electronic systems in their following design iterations. This development is associated with RADNEXT WP6 activities and will contribute to Radiation Hardness Assurance of the electronic systems deployed at the accelerator facilities, such as CERN.

Experiment test report

The advanced system-level observation methodology, studied in the framework of the PhD thesis, consists of two techniques: total current consumption observation, and the in-system analog signal monitoring. The main focus of the performed experiment was the analog signal logging part of the proposed methodology. The in-system signal sampling has a potential to diagnose the component-level performance within the System Under Test (SUT), which gives a more realistic estimate of SEE rates and TNID degradation of the utilized devices than component-level irradiation.

The test campaign performed at the Chiplr facility, which is an implementation of the TA10-317 project, concerned two case studies – SEE Tester v2 (mixed-signal SoC-based system) and RSS HV (high-voltage power supply for the radiation detector bias). The function performed by the SEE Tester v2

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during irradiation was the simultaneous SEU and SEL monitoring of an SRAM memory (Alliance AS7C34098A-10TCN), placed on the daughterboard. The RSS HV system was generating a constant voltage of +100 V with a static 10.1 MOhm load. A single SUT of SEE Tester v2 was irradiated, in the case of RSS HV three systems in total were subjected to the ChiPlr neutron beam. All tested systems were designed as radiation-tolerant and are expected to operate in the mixed-field environment of the accelerator. The objective of the system-level test was the irradiation of all SUTs up to their expected lifetime neutron fluences (in this case, the neutron fluence represents the complete high-energy hadron fluence of the accelerator environment). All SUT were irradiated continuously up to the total high-energy neutron (>10 MeV) fluence of $1 \cdot 10^{12}$ n/cm². Due to the technical problems of the RAL accelerator complex, which is unrelated to the ChiPlr facility operations, the test campaign was split between two parts, performed in June and September 2024.

The analog signal monitoring was implemented by placing a total of 12 analog signal probes in SEE Tester v2, and 6 signal probes in each of two RSS HV SUTs. The data acquisition setup was designed for capturing of both cumulative and stochastic effects in the tested systems. Both types of effects were expected in the atmospheric neutron field of ChiPlr, as these particles can induce the Displacement Damage (DD) as well as the Single-Event Effects (SEEs) in semiconductor devices. All the monitored signals were conditioned using a custom-designed radiation-tolerant buffering system (Buffers Box) and brought to the input channels of the fast VME digitizers (250 MSps ADCs with 12-bit resolution).

Figure 1. Test installation during the system-level test at the ChiPlr facility.

The total received high-energy neutron fluence by the end of the test campaign was equal to $1 \cdot 10^{12}$ n/cm², and the 1 MeV neutron equivalent fluence, which characterizes the Displacement Damage in electronic circuits, was around $1.72 \cdot 10^{12}$ neq/cm². The SEE Tester v2 system did not suffer from any destructive failures and remained functional throughout the test campaign. However, multiple failure modes were observed, which were grouped in two classes: failures transparent to the system, which did not influence its main functionality, and losses of functionality, which disturbed the main function of the Tester, which is the SEU and SEL monitoring of the SRAM device. Furthermore, multiple errors were detected in the post-test data analysis, by analysing the data retrieved from the system during irradiation. All of them turned out to be transparent to the system. The counts of all failure modes are presented in Table 1.

Transparent to the system			Soft or hard loss of functionality			Total
Address error	Timestamp error	Periodic data error	Loss of communication	SEL detection failure	Reduced functionality	
5	2	1	41	2	29	90

Table 1. Counts of failure modes observed in SEE Tester v2 during the Chiplr test campaign

During the test, the detailed waveforms were recorded only during the transient effect occurrences. For this purpose, all the monitored voltages were constantly compared with the threshold values set at $\pm 10\%$ of the nominal levels. The monitoring of the SEE Tester v2 was largely focused on its power supply system, where multiple transient effects were detected at the outputs of the DC-DC converters. Moreover, the cascades of Single-Event Transients (SETs) were observed, since the voltage disturbances were propagating to the linear regulators, which are connected to the outputs of the primary DC-DC converters. It was seen, that the SUTs can propagate through both *Input* and *Control* voltage channels of these regulators (Fig. 2).

Based on the performed component-level observations, a connection could be established between the effects observed on the system level, and the SETs which were taking place in the particular electronic components. For example, in the case of the “Loss of communication” failure mode, 48.8% of events were caused by the SETs in the +2.0V regulator, and 29.3% of events were associated with the SETs in the outputs of the +3.3V regulator. Both power lines are required for the proper operation of the central processing unit of the SEE Tester v2 – SmartFusion2 System-on-a-Chip. The observed disturbances were causing a reset of this component, after which it would enter an unconfigured state or a functional interrupt, incompatible with the normal system performance.

Figure 2. The cascade of Single-Event Transients originating from the +3.3V line of SEE Tester v2, recorded during the Chiplr test campaign (right), and a fragment of the power delivery circuit of the system, demonstrating the propagation of voltage disturbances (left).

The monitoring of the RSS HV system concerned six signals in total: four voltages in the stabilization loop of the regulator, the output voltage, measured through the 100:1 resistor divider, and the output of the +5.0V regulator, which provides power to the operational amplifiers utilized in the design. Among all the monitored signals, the SETs were detected only on two lines belonging to the stabilization loop of RSS HV. One of them is the output voltage of the LM358 operational amplifier, another one is the emitter of the BC817 pnp transistor. Noticeably, a large difference in SET rates was observed between two irradiated SUTs. It was around two orders of magnitude higher in the case of the first one, which also suffered from an unrecoverable failure at the total cumulated fluence of $3.30 \cdot 10^{11} \text{ n/cm}^2$. This system was replaced after the first part of the test campaign with a pristine one. Based on the recorded

SET waveforms, it was determined that the observed system-level failure was caused by an excessive oscillation of the output voltage of the regulator (Fig. 3), triggered by an SET with high amplitude at the output of the LM358 operational amplifier. Multiple such failures were observed, but only in the SUT that ultimately suffered from a catastrophic event. Apart from such cases, all other SETs exerted a negligible effect on the output voltage of all irradiated RSS HV systems. The final SET cross-sections, also for the SEE Tester v2's DC-DC regulators, are reported in Figure 4.

Figure 3. The waveforms of Single-Event Transients recorded in the RS HV system. The left figure presents a decreasing voltage pulse at the emitter of the pnp transistor, the right figure shows a voltage oscillation observed in one of the systems. One of such oscillations caused an unrecoverable failure of the system.

In summary, the performed analog signal observations gave a detailed insight into the operation of two different systems in the atmospheric neutron field. Through the component-level monitoring, it was possible to determine the error propagation mechanisms and connect them with the observations performed on the system level. Furthermore, the circuit disturbances leading to the catastrophic failure of one of the systems were studied with the help of the data collected through the analog signal monitoring. In both SEE Tester v2 and RSS HV, multiple sensitive components were determined which have a high contribution to the total failure rates of the irradiated systems. This information presents valuable feedback for the possible system design modifications, aimed to improve the robustness of the concerned radiation-tolerant designs. This test campaign also became a successful evaluation of the new analog signal sampling system, designed in the framework of the PhD research for the purposes of observability enhancement during system-level testing of diverse accelerator electronics.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	
Data for Thesis	X
Follow-up experiment at same facility	
Follow-up experiment at another facility	
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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